

Impact Engineering Team
Solid Mechanics and Materials Engineering Group

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MODELLING OF A POLYMER COMPOSITE TUBE CRUSHING PROCESS UNDER HIGH STRAIN RATE CONDITIONS

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Experiments

Tube Crashing – setup

Configuration of drop tower

2. Experiments

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2. Experiments

2.2 Tube Crashing – setup

- Laminates of two different layup angles will be manufactured: $\pm 45^\circ$ and $\sim \pm 60^\circ$
- 2 different chamfer shapes will be prepared

2 x layups, 2 chamfers, 1 energy level, 3 repeats = 12 specimens

8 spare specimens

Different chamfer shapes

Tube Crushing Data set

- Tube crushing data set are provided for $\pm 45^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ / \pm 30^\circ$ tubes.
- Samples include inner chamfer case and outer chamfer case.
- Each case was tried for 4 times which generates data set of 16 specimens.

Failure of $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates

Failure of $\pm 45^\circ / \pm 30^\circ$ laminates

Tube Crushing Data set

- Tube crushing data set

Tube Crushing Data set

- Tube crushing data set

Viscoelastic Model

Experimental evidence

Observed and quantified rate dependent behaviour of CFRP requires implementation of rate dependent models for numerical simulations of the response of CFRP to impact loading.

(a) transverse tensile modulus E_{2T}

(b) transverse tensile strength Y_T

(c) transverse compressive modulus E_{2C}

(d) transverse compressive strength Y_C

(e) in-plane shear modulus G_{12}

(f) in-plane shear strength S_L

Viscoelastic Model

$$E_1(\dot{\epsilon}) = E_1^0 = \text{constant}$$

$$E_2(\dot{\epsilon}) = E_2^0 f_e(\dot{\epsilon})$$

$$G_{12}(\dot{\epsilon}) = G_{12}^0 f_e(\dot{\epsilon})$$

$$X_T(\dot{\epsilon}) = X_T^0 = \text{constant}$$

$$X_C(\dot{\epsilon}) = X_C^0 f_u(\dot{\epsilon})$$

$$Y_T(\dot{\epsilon}) = Y_T^0 f_u(\dot{\epsilon})$$

$$Y_C(\dot{\epsilon}) = Y_C^0 f_u(\dot{\epsilon})$$

$$S_L(\dot{\epsilon}) = S_L^0 f_u(\dot{\epsilon})$$

All elastic and strength properties need to be rate dependent (i.e. functions of strain rate) to meet the requirements posed by experimental observation and quantification.

Elastic Properties

Strength Properties

Viscoelastic Model

Property type	m	n
Elastic	1.60×10^{-4}	2
Strength	1.13×10^{-4}	4

$$\sigma^x = K_d^{x dy} (\epsilon^x - \epsilon_{vp}^x).$$

$$K_d^{x dy} = K_d^x (E_{ij}^{dy}, X_{ij}^{dy}),$$

$$E_{ij}^{dy} = E_{ij} f(\dot{\epsilon})$$

$$f(\dot{\epsilon}) = 1 + m(\dot{\epsilon})^{\frac{1}{n}}$$

At this stage of model development, this mathematical form has been implemented to make the elastic and strength properties rate dependent.

“Viscoplastic” Model - Failure Criteria

This failure criteria is takes into account the physical behaviour of unidirectionally reinforced polymer matrix composites, by resolving the global stress state into the local/material coordinate system where a number of smaller length scale physical phenomena is represented.

$$F_{1+} = \phi_{1+} - r_{1+} \leq 0;$$

$$F_{1-} = \phi_{1-} - r_{1-} \leq 0,$$

$$F_{2+} = \phi_{2+} - r_{2+} \leq 0;$$

$$F_{2-} = \phi_{2-} - r_{2-} \leq 0.$$

$$\phi_{1+} = \frac{\sigma_{11}}{X^T},$$

$$\phi_{1-} = \left\langle \frac{\tau_{12}^m + \eta^L \sigma_{22}^m}{S_{is}^L} \right\rangle,$$

$$\langle x \rangle = (x + |x|)/2$$

Fiber direction

$$\phi_{1-} = (1 - g) \frac{\sigma_{22}^m}{Y_{is}^T} + g \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}^m}{Y_{is}^T} \right)^2 + g \cdot \left(\frac{\tau_{12}^m}{S_{is}^L} \right)^2.$$

“Viscoplastic” Model - Failure Criteria

This failure criteria is proposed for implementation into the current model in order to provide the ability to simulate non-linear behaviour of composites subjected to impact loading.

- Larc Failure Criteria

$$\phi_{2+} = (1 - g) \frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_{is}^T} + g \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_{is}^T} \right)^2 + g \left(\frac{\tau_{12}^m}{S_{is}^L} \right)^2,$$

Matrix direction

$$\phi_{2-} = \left(\frac{\tau_{eff}^T}{S^T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{eff}^L}{S_{is}^L} \right)^2.$$

$$\phi_{2-} = \left(\frac{\tau_{eff}^{mT}}{S^T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{eff}^{mL}}{S_{is}^L} \right)^2.$$

More details about failure criteria:

<http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0021998305046452>

“Viscoplastic” Model - Failure Criteria

This failure criteria is represented by a complex ‘failure’ or ‘yield’ surface which is capable of representing the complex mechanical behaviour of heterogeneous UD FRP...

“Viscoplastic” Model - Damage Evolution

Stiffness Degradation:

$$\mathbf{H} = \frac{\partial G^2}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma} \otimes \boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{(1-d_1)E_1} & \frac{-\nu_{21}}{E_2} & 0 \\ \frac{-\nu_{12}}{E_1} & \frac{1}{(1-d_2)E_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-d_6)G_{12}} \end{bmatrix}$$

...including damage which manifests itself as strain softening at Meso-II length scale. The evolve based on energy dissipation rate

Damage Laws:

$$d_{1+} = 1 - (1 - d_{1+}^L)(1 - d_{1+}^E),$$

$$d_{1-}^* = 1 - \frac{1}{r_{1-}} \exp[A_{1-}(1 - r_{1-})],$$

$$d_{2+} = 1 - \frac{1}{f_{2+}(r_{2+})} \exp[A_{2+}(1 - f_{2+}(r_{2+}))],$$

$$d_{2-} = 1 - \frac{1}{r_{2-}} \exp[A_{2-}(1 - r_{2-})],$$

$$d_6^*(r_{2+}) = 1 - \frac{1}{r_{2-}} \exp[A_6(1 - r_{2+})],$$

$$d_{1+}^L = 1 + \frac{K_1}{E_1} - \left(\frac{K_1}{E_1} + 1\right) \frac{1}{r_{1+}^L},$$

$$d_{1+}^E = 1 - \frac{1}{r_{1+}^E} \exp[A_{1+}(1 - r_{1+}^E)],$$

Damage Variables:

More details about damage model:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167663607000543>

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Validation: Tube Crushing

- LS-DYNA
- VUMAT
- 35 Material constants
- 61 state variables
- 3D Solid
- Boundary condition: V_z

Material Card

2	properties are reserved by LS-Dyna Material properties required: 50	20	fGT --> MODE I Longitudinal fracture energy, pull out
	LMC (40)		G_XC --> MODE I Longitudinal compression fracture
1	IBULK (Dyna reserve) --> Address of bulk modulus in material constants array	21	energy
2	IG (Dyna reserve) --> Address of shear modulus in material constants array	22	fGC --> MODE I Longitudinal
	ELASTIC PROPERTIES 4	23	G_YT --> MODE I Transverse fracture energy
3	E11 --> Longitudinal Young modulus (fiber direction)	24	G_YC --> Transverse Compression fracture energy
	E22 --> Transverse Young modulus (matrix direction)	25	G_SL --> MODE II Transverse fracture energy
4	direction)		HYGROSCOPIC MOISTURE 3 *see note
5	G12 --> Shear modulus (in-plane)		BETA11 --> Longitudinal coefficient of hygroscopic absorption
6	v12 --> Major Poisson ratio	26	BETA22 --> Transverse coefficient of hygroscopic absorption
	THERMAL 2	27	DM --> Moisture increment
7	ALPHA11 --> Longitudinal coefficient of thermal dilatation		VISCOSITY RETARDATION TIME 1
8	ALPHA22 --> Transverse coefficient of thermal dilatation	28	ETA --> Viscosity retardation time (positive and close to 0)
	PLASTIC SHEAR 2		for 3D elements* (for 2D prop(28)and (29) should be entered 0)
9	SLP--> Yield stress	30	V23 --> Coeficiente de Poisson
10	Akplastic--> Plastic stiffness	31	THIC --> Espesor del elemento (en dirección 3)
	STRENGTH 8	32-34	null
11	XT --> Longitudinal tensile strength		rate_ke --> multiplier parameter for elastic properties under high rates
12	fXT --> fXT*XT--> pull out stress	35	rate_ku --> multiplier parameter for strength properties under high rates
13	XC --> Longitudinal compressive strength	36	rate_ne --> exponent parameter for elastic properties under high rates
14	fXC --> fXC*XC--> Stress second slope	37	rate_nu --> exponent parameter for strength properties under high rates
15	YT --> Transverse tensile strength (In-situ)	38	rate_damp --> damping factor for viscoelasticity
16	YC --> Transverse compressive strength	39	rate_max --> Maximum allowable strain rate
	ALPHA0 --> Fracture angle (RADIANS)of transverse comp. strength		LMCA (12)
17	transverse comp. strength	1_10	null
18	SL --> In-plane shear strength (In-situ)	11	idysw If equals 1 , it activates rate dependency
	FRACTURE ENERGY 7	12	idamsw If equals 1 , rate dependency stops after failure
19	G_XT --> MODE I Longitudinal fracture energy, break		

State Variables

hsvs(1) := MAX(pfT): Fiber tension internal
hsvs(2) := MAX(pmT): Matrix tension internal
hsvs(3) := MAX(pfC): Fiber compression internal
hsvs(4) := MAX(pmC): Matrix compression internal

hsvs(5) := rdummy
hsvs(6) := rdummy
hsvs(7) := DAMAGE INDEX: 3:Fiber+Matrix, 2:fiber, 1: matrix
hsvs(8) := d1 damage parameter in fiber direction
hsvs(9) := d2 damage parameter in matrix direction
hsvs(10):= d6 damage parameter in shear direction
hsvs(11):= STRENGTH REDUCTION
Strength reduction: XT XC YC YT
(each digit is the strength reduction)

hsvs(12):= fiber dissipated energy $gf=g1$
hsvs(13):= matrix dissipated energy $gm=g2+g6$
hsvs(14):= strain(1)
hsvs(15):= strain(2)
hsvs(16):= strain(3)
hsvs(17):= strain(4)
hsvs(18):= strain(5)
hsvs(19):= strain(6)

hsvs(20):=element status (1 - Active, 0 - Deleted)
hsvs(22-41) = Null
hsvs(k,42)=epdot(1)
hsvs(k,43)=epdot(2)
hsvs(k,44)=epdot(3)
hsvs(k,45)=epdot(4)
hsvs(k,46)=epdot(5)
hsvs(k,47)=epdot(6)
hsvs(k,48)=Dynamic minus static E2
hsvs(k,49)=Dynamic minus static G12
hsvs(k,50)=Dynamic minus static XC
hsvs(k,51)=Dynamic minus static YT
hsvs(k,52)=Dynamic minus static YC
hsvs(k,53)=Dynamic minus static SL
hsvs(k,54)=activation of damage in any mode equal 1 otherwise 0
hsvs(55-61) = Null

Validation: Tube Crushing

- 16 parts
- 256000 elements
- 274720 nodes

Validation: Tube Crushing

